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Abstract:

In this paper, we discuss the stability of stochastic type differential equations through obtaining the stability condition for the respective stochastic difference equation. The system formulation is done by considering the stochastic differential equation that describes the dynamics of single isolated neuron involving delay. Here the discretization of the stochastic differential equation is done through the Euler- Maruyama Method. And the desired stability is obtained by applying suitable assumptions and through the help of theorems. The obtained theoretical results are represented through numerical simulation using MATLAB

Key Words: Difference Equation, Stochastic Difference Equation, Martingale Sequence, Lyapunov-Krasovkii Functional & Neural Networks.

1. Introduction:

Difference equations have attracted much attention due to their applications in many areas of real world problems. In particular, difference equation in neural networks with delays have established many applications in specific fields such as signal processing, image processing, pattern recognition, associative memory and optimization problems. These applications strongly depend on the stability of the equilibrium point of the system designed. Thus, the stability analysis is necessary for the design and applications in digital signal processing. In hardware enactment of recurrent neural networks, time delays happen due to finite switching speed of the amplifiers and communication time. In current years, significant number of research works has been rendered to study the global asymptotic or exponential stability for the neural networks with time delays via Lyapunov function method. Especially, growing interest exists in the study of differential equations with both discrete and distributed delays, see [5, 6]. And also, during the execution of the computation, there are many stochastic disturbances that disturb the stability of a designed system. A designed system could be stabilized or destabilized by convinced stochastic inputs. However, besides stochastic effects, impulsive effects as well exist in real systems. Therefore, it is essential to ruminate both impulsive and stochastic effect on system of difference equations [10, 11]. In the case of linear stochastic differential equations the mean-square asymptotic stability of the numerical method has been studied by several authors e.g., [6, 11]. But the almost sure asymptotic stability of numerical method has been less studied. Inspired by the above discussions, the main objective of this paper is to study the global asymptotic stability of system of difference equation describing the dynamics of a neuron. In this paper we consider the almost sure asymptotic stability of the strong Euler-Maruyama method to the nonlinear scalar stochastic differential equation. It shows that achieved difference equation is a worthy discrete model, since under the conditions from Theorem 4.1, solutions of the continuous problem have the same asymptotic behavior. We establish new stability conditions for the stochastic difference equation with the help of Lyapunov-Krasovkii functional method and some well-known inequalities. An example with numerical simulation results are given to show the effectiveness of the proposed stability result.

2. Preliminaries:

In this section we recall the necessary definitions and lemmas that will be used to prove our results. Take $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}, \mathbb{P})$ to be a complete filtered probability space. Let $\{\xi_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence of independent random variables with $E\xi_k = 0$ and $E\xi_k^2 = 1$. We assume that our filter $\{\mathcal{F}_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is naturally generated and takes the form $\mathcal{F}_{k+1} = \sigma\{\xi_{i+1}, i = 0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$.

Here we consider a sequence of random variables $\{Y_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$. A discrete time stochastic sequence $\{Y_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is said to be $\mathcal{F}_k$ -martingale if it satisfies for any time k , $E(Y_k | \mathcal{F}_{k-1}) < \infty$ and $E(Y_{k+1} | \mathcal{F}_k) = Y_{k+1}$. A real valued process Y defined on a filtered space $(\Omega, \mathcal{F}, \{\mathcal{F}_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}, \mathbb{P})$ is called a *seimartingale* if it can be decomposed as $Y_k = M_k + A_k$ where M is a local martingale A is adapted process of a bounded variation. And the stochastic sequence $\{\xi_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is said to be $\mathcal{F}_k$ -martingale difference, if $E(|\xi_k|) < \infty$ and $E(\xi_{k+1} | \mathcal{F}_k) = 0$ almost surely $\forall k \in \mathbb{N}$.

3. Mathematical Formulation:

The following represents the system of stochastic differential equation which describes the dynamics of an isolated neuron described in terms of delay differential equations

$$dy(t) = [-y(t) + \alpha\varphi(y(t) - \beta y(t - \tau))]dt + \psi(t, y(t - \tau))dW_t, \quad t \geq 0 \quad (1)$$

Where $y(t)$ – is the activation level of a neuron at a time t

α – is constant describing the range of the variable $y(t)$

β – is the measure that describes the influence of past history

τ – represents the delay

φ – activation function of the neuron

ψ – noise intensity.

W_t – Wiener process

and the constants $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}^+$, $\beta \geq 0$ and $\tau \in [0, \infty)$. And the above system forms a model of neural network.

The stability of the above system is obtained by considered the related discretized form of equation. Hence the discretization of the above model through Euler-Maruyama is given by

$$Y_{k+1} = (1-d)Y_k + \alpha d\phi(Y_k - \beta Y_{k-\tau}) + \sqrt{d}\psi_{k,Y_{k-\tau}}\xi_{k+1}, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0 \quad (2)$$

With $Y_0 \in \mathbb{R}$ -as arbitrary nonrandom initial value. $d \in (0,1]$ is the mesh size. ϕ -is continuous real valued function such that

$$|\phi(x)| \leq |x| \quad (3)$$

$$\text{And } |\alpha|(1 + |\beta|) < 1 \quad (4)$$

ξ_k -are independent random variables suitably chosen with mean $E\xi_k = 0$ and variance given by unit, $E\xi_k^2 = 1$.

4. Main Results:

Lemma 4.1: Let $\{x_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence of independent $\mathcal{F}_k$ -measurable random variables, $E[x_k] = 0$ and $E|x_k| < \infty = 0$. Let also $\{y_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a sequence of $\mathcal{F}_k$ -measurable random variables such that $E|y_{k-1}|x_k| < \infty$ for all $k \geq 1$. Then $\{Z_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$,

$$Z_k = \sum_{s=1}^k y_{s-1} x_s$$

For all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, is an $\mathcal{F}_k$ -martingale and $\{y_{k-1}x_k\}$ is an $\mathcal{F}_k$ -martingale difference.

Lemma 4.2: Let $\{W_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ be a non-negative $\mathcal{F}_k$ -martingale process, $E|W_k| < \infty \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$ and

$$W_{k+1} \leq W_k + u_k - v_k + v_{k+1}, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0,$$

Where $\{v_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is an $\mathcal{F}_k$ -martingale difference, $\{u_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}, \{v_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ are nonnegative $\mathcal{F}_k$ -martingale process, $E|u_k|, E|v_k| < \infty \forall k \in \mathbb{N}$. Then

$$\{\omega: \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} u_k < \infty\} \subseteq \{\omega: \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} v_k < \infty\} \cap \{W_k \rightarrow\}.$$

By $\{W_k \rightarrow\}$ we refer to the set of all $\omega \in \Omega$, such that $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} W_k(\omega) = 0$ exists and is finite.

Theorem 4.1: Let Y_k be the solution of the equation (2) with the conditions

$$|\psi_{k,Y_k}| \leq \gamma_k |Y_k|^2 + \eta_k^2, \quad \psi_{k,0} = 0 \quad (5)$$

Where $\sum_{i=1}^{\infty} \eta_i^2 < \infty$ and

$$\alpha^2(1 + |\beta|)^2 + \gamma_k < 1 \quad (6)$$

Satisfied by equation (4). Then $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} Y_k = 0$ almost everywhere.

Proof: Consider equation (2),

$$Y_{k+1} = (1-d)Y_k + \alpha d\phi(Y_k - \beta Y_{k-\tau}) + \sqrt{d}\psi_{k,Y_{k-\tau}}\xi_{k+1}, \quad k \in \mathbb{N}_0$$

Squaring on both sides we get

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{k+1}^2 &= [(1-d)Y_k + \alpha d\phi(Y_k - \beta Y_{k-\tau})]^2 + 2[(1-d)Y_k + \alpha d\phi(Y_k - \beta Y_{k-\tau})]\sqrt{d}\psi_{k,Y_{k-\tau}}\xi_{k+1} + d\psi_{k,Y_{k-\tau}}^2\xi_{k+1}^2 \\ &= [(1-d)Y_k + \alpha d\phi(Y_k - \beta Y_{k-\tau})]^2 + d\psi_{k,Y_{k-\tau}}^2 + \delta_{k+1}. \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

Where $\{\delta_k\}_{k \in \mathbb{N}}$ is an $\mathcal{F}_n$ -martingale difference, and its value is defined as

$$\delta_{k+1} = 2[(1-d)Y_k + \alpha d\phi(Y_k - \beta Y_{k-\tau})]\sqrt{d}\psi_{k,Y_{k-\tau}}\xi_{k+1} + d\psi_{k,Y_{k-\tau}}^2\{\xi_{k+1}^2 - 1\} \quad (8)$$

Also from our assumption we have $E\xi_k^2 = 1$. Hence $\{E\xi_k^2 - 1\}$ $\mathcal{F}_{k+1}$ -martingale-difference. And from the lemma we conclude that δ_{k+1} is $\mathcal{F}_{k+1}$ -martingale-difference.

Consider

$$\sum_{i=1}^n x_i y_i \leq \sum_{i=1}^n |x_i y_i| \leq \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{|x_i|}(\sqrt{|x_i|} |y_i|)$$

Now from Holder's inequality we have

$$\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i y_i| \leq \sum_{i=1}^n \sqrt{|x_i|}(\sqrt{|x_i|} |y_i|) \leq \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i|} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n |x_i| |y_i|^2}$$

Now consider,

$$\begin{aligned} |(1-d)Y_k + \alpha d\phi(Y_k - \beta Y_{k-\tau})| &\leq |(1-d)Y_k| + |\alpha d|\phi(Y_k - \beta Y_{k-\tau})| \\ &\leq |(1-d)Y_k| + |\alpha d||Y_k - \beta Y_{k-\tau}| \\ &\leq (1-d)|Y_k| + |\alpha d|(|Y_k| + |\beta||Y_{k-\tau}|) \\ &\leq (1-d + |\alpha d|)|Y_k| + |\alpha d|\beta||Y_{k-\tau}| \end{aligned}$$

Here let $n = 2x_1 = 1-d + |\alpha d|$, $y_1 = |Y_k|$, $x_2 = |\alpha d|\beta|$, $y_2 = |Y_{k-\tau}|$,

$$\leq [1-d + |\alpha d| + |\alpha d|\beta|][1-d + |\alpha d|]|Y_k|^2 + |\alpha d|\beta||Y_{k-\tau}|^2 \quad (9)$$

Substituting (9) in (7) we have

$$\begin{aligned} Y_{k+1}^2 &\leq [1-d + |\alpha d| + |\alpha d|\beta|][1-d + |\alpha d|]|Y_k|^2 + |\alpha d|\beta||Y_{k-\tau}|^2 + d\psi_{k,Y_{k-\tau}}^2 + \delta_{k+1} \\ &\leq [1-d + |\alpha d| + |\alpha d|\beta|][1-d + |\alpha d|]|Y_k|^2 + |\alpha d|\beta||Y_{k-\tau}|^2 + d\gamma_k |Y_k|^2 + d\eta_k^2 + \delta_{k+1} \\ &\leq [(1-d + |\alpha d| + |\alpha d|\beta|)][1-d + |\alpha d|]|Y_k|^2 + |\alpha d|\beta||Y_{k-\tau}|^2 + d\gamma_k |Y_k|^2 + d\eta_k^2 + \delta_{k+1} \\ &\leq [(1-d + |\alpha d| + |\alpha d|\beta|)(1-d + |\alpha d|) + d\gamma_k]|Y_k|^2 + [d|\alpha|\beta|(1-d + |\alpha d| + |\alpha d|\beta|)]|Y_{k-\tau}|^2 + d\eta_k^2 + \delta_{k+1} \end{aligned}$$

Let $a = d|\alpha|\beta|(1-d + |\alpha d| + |\alpha d|\beta|)$

Let

$$\begin{aligned} V(k)^{(1)} &= a \sum_{s=k-\tau}^{k-1} Y_s^2 \\ V(k) &= Y_k^2 + V(k)^{(1)} \end{aligned}$$

Consider, $\Delta V(k)^{(1)} = V(k+1)^{(1)} - V(k)^{(1)}$

$$\begin{aligned} &= a \sum_{s=k+1-\tau}^k Y_s^2 - a \sum_{s=k-\tau}^{k-1} Y_s^2 \\ &= a Y_k^2 - a Y_{k-\tau}^2 \end{aligned}$$

Now consider

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta V(k) &= Y_{k+1}^2 - Y_k^2 + \Delta V(k)^{(1)} \\ &= Y_{k+1}^2 - Y_k^2 + aY_k^2 - aY_{k-\tau}^2 \\ &\leq [(1-d + |\alpha|d + |\alpha|d|\beta|)(1-d + |\alpha|d) + d\gamma_k]|Y_k|^2 + [d|\alpha||\beta|(1-d + |\alpha|d + |\alpha|d|\beta|)]|Y_{k-\tau}|^2 + d\eta_k^2 \\ &\quad + \delta_{k+1} - Y_k^2 + aY_k^2 - aY_{k-\tau}^2 \\ &\leq [a-1 + (1-d + |\alpha|d + |\alpha|d|\beta|)(1-d + |\alpha|d) + d\gamma_k]|Y_k|^2 + d\eta_k^2 + \delta_{k+1} \\ &\leq [d|\alpha||\beta|(1-d + |\alpha|d + |\alpha|d|\beta|) - 1 + (1-d + |\alpha|d + |\alpha|d|\beta|)(1-d + |\alpha|d) + d\gamma_k]|Y_k|^2 + d\eta_k^2 + \delta_{k+1} \\ &\leq ([1-d(1-|\alpha|(1+|\beta|))]^2 - 1 + d\gamma_k)|Y_k|^2 + d\eta_k^2 + \delta_{k+1} \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

From (6) and for all $d \in (0,1]$ we get,

$$0 < 1 - |\alpha|(1 + |\beta|) < 1, 0 < d[1 - |\alpha|(1 + |\beta|)] < 1$$

$$\Rightarrow 0 < 1 - d[1 - |\alpha|(1 + |\beta|)] < |\alpha|(1 + |\beta|)$$

Therefore, $(1 - d[1 - |\alpha|(1 + |\beta|)])^2 + d\gamma_k \leq \alpha^2(1 + |\beta|)^2 + d\gamma_k < 1$.

Let us denote $\xi = (1 - [1 - d(1 - |\alpha|(1 + |\beta|))]^2 - d\gamma_k)$

From (10), we have $\Delta V(k) \leq ([1 - d(1 - |\alpha|(1 + |\beta|))]^2 - 1 + d\gamma_k)|Y_k|^2 + d\eta_k^2 + \delta_{k+1}$

$$V(k+1) \leq V(k) - \xi Y_k^2 + d\eta_k^2 + \delta_{k+1} \tag{11}$$

And let, $W_k = V(k)$, $u_k = d\eta_k^2$, $v_k = \xi Y_k^2$ and $v_{k+1} = \delta_{k+1}$

Applying lemma 4.2 we have,

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} V(k) \text{ and } \xi \lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} \sum_{s=1}^k Y_s^2$$

Exists and are almost surely finite

Our intension is to prove $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} Y_k = 0$. Let us assume that suppose $\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} Y_k \neq 0$ with non zero probability. Then we can find a set Ω such that $Y_{k_l}^2 > \zeta(x)$, $l \in \mathbb{N}$, $x \in \Omega$

Define,

$$\psi(k, x) = \text{number of sequence } \{k_n(x)\} \leq k$$

For all $k \in \mathbb{N}$, $x \in \Omega$. And $\psi(k, x) \rightarrow \infty$ as $k \rightarrow \infty$. Hence we arrive at a contradiction, for $x \in \Omega$

$$\infty > \xi \sum_{s=1}^k Y_s^2(x) \geq \xi \sum_{s_l \leq k} Y_{s_l}^2(x) \geq \zeta(x) \xi \psi(k, x) \rightarrow \infty, k \rightarrow \infty$$

This is a contradiction. Therefore we have

$$\lim_{k \rightarrow \infty} Y_k = 0$$

Hence the theorem is proved

5. Numerical Example:

In this section, we provide a numerical example to demonstrate the effectiveness of the proposed asymptotic stability result.

Example 5.1 Consider the following two-neuron stochastic recurrent neural networks with impulses:

$$dy(t) = [-y(t) + \alpha\varphi(y(t) - \beta y(t - \tau))]dt + \psi(t, y(t - \tau))dW_t, \quad t \geq 0, t \neq t_k \tag{12}$$

$$\Delta y(t_k) = dy(t_k), t = t_k, k = 1, 2, \dots$$

The activation function of the neuron is given by $\varphi(x) = \tanh(0.7) - 0.1 \sin x$, delay $\tau(t) = 0.5 + 0.5 \sin t$, $\alpha = \begin{bmatrix} -0.4 & 0.3 \\ 0.5 & 0.1 \end{bmatrix}$

$$, \beta = \begin{bmatrix} 0.2 & -0.4 \\ -0.1 & 0.5 \end{bmatrix}$$

And here it is clear that the activation function and constants satisfies our assumptions.

Numerical Simulation:

Figure 2: State responses of $y_1(t), y_2(t)$ of the system (12) With impulsive effects.

Thus the system (12) satisfies all the conditions stated in Theorem 4.1. Hence the given stochastic neural network (12) with the impulsive effect is globally asymptotically stable.

6. Conclusion:

In this paper, the problem of stability behavior for a system of stochastic difference equation that describes the dynamics of single isolated neuron involving delay has been investigated by the use of Lyapunov method. By constructing an appropriate Lyapunov function and combined with stochastic analysis approach, a new set of sufficient conditions have been obtained to

confirm the global asymptotic stability of the addressed neural networks. Further this paper can also be extended to study the global exponential stability of the equilibrium point. Finally, a numerical example is given to show the effectiveness of our stability result.

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